

Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-4'-Hydroxyaniline Complexes with Mg^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+}

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Potentiometric studies on metal complexes of Mg^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-hydroxyaniline have been carried out. The proton-ligand dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at an ionic strength 0.1 M in 75 : 25 percent (v/v) dioxane-water medium.

THE successive stability constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-hydroxyaniline with bivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹ and the results are presented here.

A precision research pH meter, Corning Model 12, with combined glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements. Both electrodes dip into the titrating mixture without vitiating any results. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scales. The changes in the pH can be measured with an accuracy of 0.005 pH unit.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-hydroxyaniline was prepared and repeatedly crystallised to obtain an analytically pure sample with m.p. 224° (Lit. m.p. 224°)².

The dioxane used was purified by the method described by Vogel³. Distilled water redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate was used throughout the investigation.

The medium of titration was 75 : 25 per cent dioxane-water (v/v) mixture. A constant ionic strength was maintained by adding sodium perchlorate. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through the solutions. The free acid, the free acid plus the ligand and the mixture of metal ion containing the acid plus the ligand were titrated against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide. Metal ion solutions of nickel and magnesium were prepared by taking the metal carbonates of A. R. grade, and those of copper and zinc were prepared by taking the metal oxides of A. R. grade. These were standardised complexometrically⁴ by EDTA titrations. All measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.07 M) solution.

- (i) 5 ml 0.16 M $HClO_4$ + 5 ml 0.64 M $NaClO_4$ + 30 ml dioxane.
- (ii) 5 ml 0.16 M $HClO_4$ + 5 ml 0.64 M $NaClO_4$ + requisite amount of reagent to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxane.
- (iii) 5 ml 0.64 M $NaClO_4$ + 5 ml metal salt 0.008 M solution in 0.16 M $HClO_4$ + the requisite amount of the reagent to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxane.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti was applied to find out the value of $\bar{n}$ and pL . The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be pointed out here that the ligand used in this study did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titration and by the absence of any significant drift in the pH even after 1 hr.

In the ligand, it is the phenolic OH group that takes part in the complex formation and the ligand behaves as monoprotic.

From the titration curves using the solutions (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various B values, (pH meter readings), were calculated and a curve between B and the corresponding $\bar{n}_A$ values was plotted (Fig. 1). The value of pK_1^H was evaluated by half integral method as well as from the plot of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A} \right]$ vs B (Fig. 2). Both these values agree well.

Fig. 1. Formation curve of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-hydroxyaniline. Plot of $\bar{n}_A$ vs B

Fig. 2. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-hydroxyaniline. Plot of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \right]$ vs B

Fig. 3. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-hydroxyaniline. Plot of $\log \left[\frac{2 - \bar{n}_A}{\bar{n}_A - 1} \right]$ vs B

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii) $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of metal complex ion equilibria. From this $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were evaluated by the half integral method. In the

Fig. 4. Metal ligand systems of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-hydroxyaniline. Plot of $\bar{n}$ vs pL

Fig. 5. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-hydroxyaniline. Plot of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}}{1 - \bar{n}} \right]$ vs pL

case of nickel and copper systems, the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values was found to be less than 1.78 log unit and hence these were calculated by the least square method and are reported.

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability of the various metal chelates was found to be $Cu^{2+} > Co^{2+} \approx Ni^{2+} > Mg^{2+}$. This is in agreement with Murakami order⁶.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Cations	$t = 25^\circ$				
	H^+	Mg^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Cu^{2+}
$\log K_1$	10.93	5.00	7.57	7.57	9.08
$\log K_2$	3.94	—	—	6.29	7.99

For proton association (H^+), K_1 corresponds to the species LH , while for metal ions K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species ML_1 and ML_2 , respectively.

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MAYADEO & PUROHIT : DETERMINATION OF STABILITY CONSTANTS ETC.

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